

THE PURCHASING HABITS OF CONSUMERS WITH REGARD TO ONLINE SHOPPING: AN ANALYSIS OF TIRUPATTUR USERS OF FLIPKART.COM

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the consumer's buying behavioural pattern towards online shopping (specially in case of flipkart.com users in Tirupattur). Also tried to find out various attitudes of flipkart users of Tirupattur towards the online shopping. For this study survey was conducted during 1st Jan to 20th Jan 2016. The data will be collected from respondents through scheduled containing questions. The study result concluded that future of e-shopping in India especially in cities looking very bright. Flipkart.com offering best prices, good products and completely hassle-free shopping experience for our customers. The success of any e-tailer company in India is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, its unique & fair policies, and its customer relations etc.

Key Words: Consumer Buying Behavior, E-Shopping, E-Commerce, Flipkart.Com, Online Shopping In Tirupattur.

Introduction:

Similar to Internet banking or E-banking, online shopping, also known as E-shopping, is currently the newest (transformative change) trend in Indian retail. Online shopping, also known as e-tailing, has grown in popularity among Indian consumers in recent years. One excellent illustration of India's business revolution is the new idea of online shopping. We may conclude that India's e-commerce industry is presently going through a phase of rapid expansion. In India, e-commerce is a lucrative market that is just waiting to be discovered. In actuality, e-commerce includes e-tailing. Online shoppers use a web browser to buy products (such as clothing, footwear, electronic appliances, home and kitchen appliances, etc.) straight from online retailers. I think in India E-shopping or online shopping is the new buzzword. Currently we are living in the age of internet. According to a study, "About 44 percent students use Internet in India and overall 72% of young people access Internet on regular basis". Due to the vast usage of Internet, the buying patterns have been changed. It has changed the way goods are purchased and sold, resulting to the exponential growth in the number of online shoppers.

E-shopping consumer buying behaviour is another name for online shopping consumer behaviour. Research and case studies on online consumer purchasing behaviour are crucial because they provide insight into consumer needs and aid in the comprehension and analysis of online product purchases. And who makes online purchases? And how do customers feel about making purchases online? The entire idea of online shopping has, in my opinion, changed in terms of consumer purchasing patterns, and the success of e-tailers depends on a variety of factors, including product quality, popularity, distinctiveness, and branding image. Flipkart.com is an online retailer based in India. It is regarded as an online retailer. In 2007, Flipkart.com was established. And its main head office is located in Bangalore city (Karnataka State). According to a survey, flipkart.com is the India's largest E-commerce company that made online shopping. As an online shopping company flipkart.com is very popular among Indian online shoppers. Flipkart.com offering some of the best prices and a completely hassle-free shopping experience. Flipkart.com offers free home delivery, cash on delivery options, 24 x 7 customer case service, Interest-free EMI options, payment through Debit or Credit cards of their customers. Flipkart.com a E-tailer company is growing at a phenomenal pace in India.

Here in this case study I want to know about online consumer's buying behavioural pattern towards online shopping (specially in case of flipkart users in Tirupattur). This Manuscript aims to identify the respondent's perception about online shopping. The paper also analyses awareness of consumers towards online shopping. Nature of study is exploratory as well as descriptive in this study both primary & secondary data have been used.

Relevance of the Study:

Online shopping is growing and has amazing growth potential. Young people are becoming increasingly drawn to this contemporary form of shopping because of how convenient it is. According to the literature review, Tirupattur has not yet been the subject of any research in this area. In light of this context, the study was conducted in an effort to assess the level of satisfaction that young people in Tirupattur have with online shopping.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology states what procedures were employed to carry out the research study. The technical facts about the study are given below:-

Research Objectives:

To achieve the goal of the study, the following research questionnaire addressed as primary research objectives:

- The primary objective of these studies is to know about online consumer’s buying behaviours towards online shopping (specially in case of flipkart users in Tirupattur).
- To identify the respondents perception about online shopping.
- To find out various attitudes of flipkart users of Tirupattur towards the online shopping.

Research Design:

In case of research design we used exploratory as well as descriptive research design for this study.

Sampling Technique:

The convenience sampling method was applied in this case study. Source of the sample is Limited to Tirupattur. Keeping in mind the objectives of the study, a structured questionnaire was prepared for the purpose of collecting the primary Data. A part from variables like: Gender, Age and overall customer satisfaction were collected and percentage method used for this study.

Sample Size:

The present study was conducted in an Tirupattur. In case of sample size we take 50 consumers (Respondents) of flipkart.com Out of the total 50, 14 were females and rest 36 were males and the age group of the respondents between 16 to 55.

Research Instrument:

For this study we used structured questionnaire as a research instrument.

Data Types:

In the context of the current study we used both primary & secondary data.

Method of Data Collection:

Primary data have been collected with the help of structured questionnaire by respondent field survey method. In case of secondary data we used internet websites, journals, newspaper etc. For this study collected data has been processed and tabulated by the way of tables. The data was collected over a months in 1st Jan to 20th Jan 2016.

Limitation of the Study:

The results of the study are specific to the sample selected and dimensions used. Hence, they may not be generalized for overall population. Actually this study is limited in sample size.

Data Facts, Analysis and Interpretation:

Descriptive Analysis:

The descriptive statistics or percentage analysis is mainly carried out to determine the percentage of the consumers falling under each category. This analysis also helps to standardize the respondent’s opinion on various aspects. This analysis is carried out for all the questions given in the Questionnaire. As mentioned above, the study is based on a sample of 50 respondents. The demographic profile of sampled customer is shown in table 1.

Results:

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of sample customers (n=50)

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	36	72%
Female	14	28%
Occupation		
Service	26	52%
Self Employed	12	24%
Profession	10	20%
Others	2	4%
Residence		
Rural	21	42%
Urban	29	58%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

It is revealed from the table 1 that 72% of the respondents is male and 28% are female. Most of the respondents 52% occupations are service, followed by self employed 24%, profession 20% and others only 4%. Others occupation means house wife. Table 1 also illustrate that most of the respondent 58% are belong to urban areas.

Table 2: Family age group wise Analysis

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group (16-25)	25	50%

Age Group (26-35)	15	30%
Age Group (36-45)	6	12%
Age Group (46-55)	4	8%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From above table 2, we can easily analyze that most of the 50% of the respondent said, that (16-25) Age group of family members like do most online shopping with flipkart.com. 30% of the respondents says that (26-35) Age group of family members like online shopping with flipkart.com. Whenever 12% respondent said that (36-45) Age group of family members like buy products via flipkart.com and least 8% of the respondents said that in (46-55) Age group of family members like do online shopping with flipkart.com.

Table 3: Preferences wise Analysis

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Attractive prices	20	40%
Reliability	15	30%
Mass variety of Products	6	12%
Popularity	9	18%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the above table 3, we try to interpret that why respondents choose flipkart.com for online shopping. It is clear that maximum 40% respondents said that they choose online shopping with flipkart.com for attractive prices, 30% respondents said that they choose flipkart.com for its reliability, 18% choose flipkart.com for its popularity, and rest minimum 12% respondents choose flipkart.com for mass variety of products.

Table 4: Frequently wise Analysis

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Once in a Week	5	10%
Once in a Month	25	50%
Once in a Six Months	13	26%
Once a Year	7	14%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the above table 4, we can analyze that majority of the respondents i.e. 50% of respondents have bought products online once a month. 26% of respondents bought online items once in a six months. 14% of the respondents bought online product once in a year, and least 10% of the respondents bought products online in a week.

Table 5: Visit retail stores before online purchasing

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	20	40%
No	26	52%
Can't Say	4	8%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the above table5, 40% of the respondents said that they visit retail stores before online purchasing with flipkart.com to see and check actual product face, Prices etc, maximum 52% of the respondents do not visit retail stores before online purchasing with flipkart.com as they believe in flipkart.com prices, quality etc. Least 8% respondents can't say for this regard.

Table 6: Buyer's online shopping timings

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
In Festival Season	15	30%
Heavy Discount Time period	25	50%
Depend Upon mood/desire	5	10%
When need	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

Above table 6 clearly shows that most of the 50% of the respondents do like online shopping with

flipkart.com in a heavy discount time period. Whenever 30% of the respondent do shopping with flipkart.com in festive seasons and 10% of the respondents like shopping with flipkart.com when they have need and same 10% respondents do shopping when they have desire.

Table 7: Buy online products segmentation

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Apparel	15	30%
Electronic Appliances	14	28%
Home & Kitchen Appliances	8	16%
Computer Accessories	13	26%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the above table 7, it is clear that 30%, Respondents bought Apparel from flipkart.com 26% percentage of respondent purchased Accessories online shopping via flipkart.com, 28%, Respondents like to purchase Electronic goods and Least 16% Respondents like to buy home & kitchen appliances from flipkart.com.

Table 8: Dislike buy product online

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Footwear	18	36%
Perfumes	20	40%
Electronic Goods	8	16%
Apparels	4	8%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the table 8, it is clear that most of the respondents i.e. 20 respondents (40%) dislike buy perfumes on online shopping with flipkart.com. Whenever 18 respondents (36%) dislike buy footwear on online shopping with flipkart.com 16% and 8% respondents dislike buy electronic goods and apparel from flipkart.com respectively.

Table 9: Reliability Check Analysis

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
100% Reliable	25	50%
50% Reliable	20	40%
10% Reliable	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

From the above table 9, try to find out online consumer reliability status among the flipkart.com users. Majority of the 25 respondents (50%) are said that flipkart.com is 100% reliable for online shopping. 20 respondents (40%) said that flipkart.com is 50% reliable for online and rest 05 respondents i.e. 10% respondents can't say for this purpose.

Table 10: Check satisfaction level analysis

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
100% Satisfied	30	60%
50% Satisfied	12	24%
Unsatisfied	5	10%
Can't say	3	6%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

Above table 10, clearly shows that majority of the respondents i.e. 30 respondents (60%) are agree that they are 100% satisfied from online shopping with flipkart.com, 24% respondents are 50% satisfied, 10% respondents are unsatisfied from online shopping with flipkart.com and rest 6% respondents i.e. 03 respondents can't say anything for this purpose.

Table 11: Continue online shopping status

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	8	16%
Can't say	2	4%

Total	50	100%
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Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Interpretation:

Above table 11 clearly shows that majority of 80% of the respondents are like to continue online shopping with flipkart.com. Whenever 16% respondents are not like to continue online shopping with flipkart.com and 4% respondents can't say anything for this purpose.

Cross Tabulation and Chi-Square 1:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant association between gender and satisfaction level of the respondents.

Table 12: Online Shopping Items * Gender of the Respondents

Satisfaction Level	100% Satisfied	50% Satisfied	Unsatisfied	Can 'Not Say	Total
Gender					
Male	25	8	2	1	36
Female	5	4	3	2	14
Total	30	12	5	3	50

Source: Primary Data, Field Survey Method

Chi-Square Analysis:

Chi-square test (symbolically written as χ^2 -test) is a non-parametric test. It is used most frequently by marketing researcher to test hypotheses. This test is employed for testing hypotheses when distribution of population is not known and when nominal data is to be analysed.

Table 13: Chi-Square Analysis

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
25	21.60	3.4	11.56	0.535
5	8.64	-3.64	13.25	1.533
8	3.60	4.4	19.36	5.378
4	2.16	1.84	3.38	1.564
2	8.40	-6.4	40.96	4.876
3	3.36	-0.36	0.13	0.038
1	1.40	-0.4	0.16	0.114
2	0.84	1.16	1.34	1.595
$\chi^2 =$		15.633		

Table 14: Chi-Square Tests

Particular	Df	Asymp. Sig.
Chi-Square	3	15.633
No of Valid Cases		50

Thus, the calculate value of $\chi^2=15.633$ is greater than table value. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings and Concluding Remarks:

On the basis of information collected from the users of flipkart.com in Tirupattur, some important facts which come as a result of this research are as follows-

- The first and foremost finding of this study is that most No. of users are happy on online shopping with flipkart.com because most of the users responses are in favour of flipkart.com
- Most respondents (users) are satisfied for online shopping with flipkart.com. So most respondents want to continue online shopping with flikart.com, they believed in flipkart.com reliability, its policies and they said that flipkart.com is reliable e-tailer in the field of online shopping.
- On the basis of user responses we can easily analyze that users of flipkart.com (Tirupattur) mainly interested in buy online apparel- Like men's, women's and kids clothes, watches, home & kitchen appliances etc. and they dislike buy online perfumes & footwear etc. they bought products online once in a week and like to do online shopping mostly on discounted time period and festive seasons.
- Users of flipkart.com believe that flipkart.com products prices are lesser than the prices in the market.
- Mostly youngsters and youth generation (16-25 Age groups) are very much interested in online shopping with flipkart.com because they know about technology, they know about e-shopping, and they know about very well when and how purchase products from this e-tailer.
- In case of various parameters for loyalty, commitment, and reliability e-tailer most of the respondents (User's) give positive responses/view for this e-tailer (flipkart.com).
- From the above discussion, it is concluded that future of e-tailers in India looking very bright. E-tailers give us the best way to save money and time through purchasing online within the range of budget. Flipkart.com offering some of the best prices and completely hassle-free shopping experience. I think the whole concept of online shopping has altered in terms of consumer's purchasing or buying behavior

and the success of E-tailers in India is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, and its unique policies.

- From the above Table XIV Chi-Square Analysis the table calculates value of X^2 is greater than table value. The null hypothesis is accepted.

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